

Supplementary material

Supplementary material for “Enhancing sugarcane yield resilience under a changing climate: adaptive irrigation and varietal strategies in Reunion Island.”

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Fig. S1. Comparison between simulated and observed leaf area index (LAI, a), aboveground dry mass (ADM, b), stalk dry mass (DM, c), and stalk fresh mass (FM, d) in the ECOFI database (Christina et al., 2020). Observations included 29 trials with R570 varieties in ratoon crop. Observations included both data during crop growth and at harvest. Relative root mean square error (RRMSE) between observed and simulated values were included.

Fig. S2. Comparison between observed and simulated soil water content (SWC) in two simulation units from the ECOFI database under rainfed conditions and depending on the soil layer (1 to 6). Relative root mean square error (RRMSE) between observed and simulated values were included.

Fig. S3. Influence of sthydrue and Ψ_{cr} parameters coefficient of variations (CV) on water-stress reduction factor swdfRUE coefficient of variation (CV). The dashed line indicated the 13.8% coefficient of variation target for swdfRUE.

Fig. S4. Change in average daily temperature ($^{\circ}C$) in each simulated grid cell across the island between the 2060 period (a,c) or the 2090 period (b,d) and the current 2020 period in the RCP 4.5 (a,b) and 8.5 (c,d) scenarios. A gradient of color from decreasing (red) to increasing (blue) values was added.

Fig. S5. Change in average potential evapotranspiration (ETP, %) in each simulated grid cell across the island between the 2060 period (a,c) or the 2090 period (b,d) and the current 2020 period in the RCP 4.5 (a,b) and 8.5 (c,d) scenarios. A gradient of color from decreasing (red) to increasing (blue) values was added.

Fig. S6. Change in annual rainfall (%) in each simulated grid cell across the island between the 2060 period (a,c) or the 2090 period (b,d) and the current 2020 period in the RCP 4.5 (a,b) and 8.5 (c,d) scenarios. A gradient of color from decreasing (red) to increasing (blue) values was added.

Table S1. Overall trend in annual change in sugarcane yield, water-stress index (WSI), irrigation water demand (IWD), rainfall, and maximum number of consecutive dry days (CDD_X) in Reunion Island and agroclimatic zones depending on RCP scenarios. The Sen's slope is presented and Mann-Kendall trend test is presented in parenthesis with ns, *, **, and *** when p-values are non-significant or lower than 0.05, 0.01, and 0.005, respectively.

	Scenario	Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹)	WSI (y ⁻¹)	IWD (mm y ⁻¹)	Rainfall (mm y ⁻¹)	CDD _X (nb y ⁻¹)
Reunion	RCP 2.6	-0.04 (ns)	0.0005 (**)	1.23 (***)	1.62 (ns)	0.004 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.08 (*)	0.0006 (***)	1.26 (***)	-2.43 (ns)	0.008 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	0.06 (ns)	0.0013 (***)	2.74 (***)	-3.78 (ns)	0.05 (*)
HA South - Sauvage (NI)	RCP 2.6	0.01 (ns)	3e-04 (*)	1.14 (**)	2.67 (ns)	0.02 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.18 (***)	3e-04 (ns)	0.89 (*)	-5.05 (ns)	0.04 (**)
	RCP 8.5	0.16 (***)	0.0012 (***)	2.77 (***)	-9.34 (**)	0.05 (**)
HA South - Tampon (NI)	RCP 2.6	-0.08 (ns)	0.001 (**)	1.75 (***)	0.23 (ns)	0.04 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.04 (ns)	0.0012 (***)	2.07 (***)	-2.77 (ns)	0.01 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	-0.01 (ns)	0.0023 (***)	4.05 (***)	-3.58 (*)	0.09 (**)
HA South - St Louis (NI)	RCP 2.6	-0.04 (ns)	6e-04 (ns)	0.91 (ns)	1.57 (ns)	0 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.01 (ns)	0.001 (*)	1.25 (*)	-1.29 (ns)	-0.02 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	0.09 (ns)	0.0012 (***)	1.9 (***)	-0.84 (ns)	0.09 (**)
HA West (NI)	RCP 2.6	0.03 (ns)	4e-04 (ns)	0.49 (ns)	1.4 (ns)	-0.01 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.09 (ns)	9e-04 (***)	0.95 (**)	-0.15 (ns)	0.03 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	0.31 (***)	6e-04 (**)	1.22 (**)	0.44 (ns)	-0.01 (ns)
HA North-East (NI)	RCP 2.6	-0.06 (ns)	6e-04 (**)	1.42 (***)	1.4 (ns)	-0.01 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.16 (***)	5e-04 (**)	1.12 (***)	-2.7 (ns)	0 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	0.17 (***)	0.0014 (***)	2.82 (***)	-4.02 (ns)	0.03 (*)
HA East (NI)	RCP 2.6	0.07 (**)	1e-04 (*)	0.4 (**)	3.58 (ns)	-0.01 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.25 (***)	1e-04 (**)	0.39 (**)	-2.3 (ns)	0 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	0.47 (***)	3e-04 (***)	1.06 (***)	-8.76 (ns)	0.04 (***)
LA South - Sauvage (NI)	RCP 2.6	0 (ns)	3e-04 (ns)	0.88 (*)	3.77 (ns)	0 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.19 (***)	1e-04 (ns)	0.47 (ns)	-3.33 (ns)	0 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	-0.02 (ns)	0.0014 (***)	3.49 (***)	-9.01 (*)	0.06 (***)
LA South - St Pierre (I)	RCP 2.6	-0.11 (ns)	9e-04 (**)	1.93 (**)	0.32 (ns)	0.05 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	-0.05 (ns)	0.0011 (***)	2.34 (***)	-1.75 (ns)	-0.01 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	-0.18 (*)	0.002 (***)	3.91 (***)	-2.49 (*)	0.09 (**)
LA South - St Louis (I)	RCP 2.6	-0.04 (ns)	6e-04 (ns)	1.02 (ns)	1.12 (ns)	0.04 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	-0.07 (ns)	0.0011 (*)	1.59 (*)	-1.01 (ns)	-0.04 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	-0.16 (*)	0.0016 (***)	2.41 (***)	-1.13 (ns)	0.09 (*)
LA West (I)	RCP 2.6	-0.04 (ns)	5e-04 (ns)	0.79 (ns)	1.06 (ns)	-0.01 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.03 (ns)	6e-04 (*)	1.11 (*)	-0.27 (ns)	0.01 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	0.11 (*)	7e-04 (*)	1.36 (**)	0.07 (ns)	0.03 (ns)
LA North-East (NI)	RCP 2.6	-0.12 (*)	8e-04 (**)	1.71 (***)	1.69 (ns)	-0.01 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.04 (ns)	6e-04 (**)	1.44 (***)	-2.17 (ns)	0.01 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	-0.14 (**)	0.0018 (***)	3.51 (***)	-2.79 (ns)	0.03 (**)
LA South - Langevin (I)	RCP 2.6	0.03 (ns)	2e-04 (**)	1.4 (**)	2.58 (ns)	0.02 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.18 (***)	1e-04 (ns)	1.12 (*)	-5.33 (ns)	0.03 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	0.29 (***)	5e-04 (***)	3.26 (***)	-9.95 (**)	0.05 (**)
LA East (NI)	RCP 2.6	-0.02 (ns)	3e-04 (*)	0.85 (**)	3.07 (ns)	0 (ns)
	RCP 4.5	0.15 (***)	3e-04 (**)	0.71 (**)	-2.43 (ns)	0.01 (ns)
	RCP 8.5	0.16 (***)	9e-04 (***)	1.97 (***)	-6.4 (ns)	0.04 (***)

Fig. S7. Average changes in yield (Mg ha⁻¹) in each agroclimatic zone between the 2060 or 2090 period and the current period under the current irrigation regime. The current irrigation regime in each agroclimatic zone is indicated by I (irrigated areas) and NI (non-irrigated areas). The altitude range of the agroclimatic zones is indicated by LA (low altitude) and HA (high altitude). A gradient of colors was added to improve visibility.

Fig. S8. Change in sugarcane yield (Mg ha^{-1}) in each simulated grid cell across the island between the 2060 period (a,c) or the 2090 period (b,d) and the current 2020 period in the RCP 4.5 (a,b) and 8.5 (c,d) scenarios. Simulations were performed with the R570 cultivar. A gradient of color from decreasing (red) to increasing (blue) values was added.

Fig. S9. Change in sugarcane yield under automatic irrigation regime filling weekly 20, 40, and 60% of soil available water capacity (AWC) in the 2060 and 2090 periods compared to the current period and current irrigation regime (fixed dose of 15mm w⁻¹ in irrigated areas), under the three RCP scenarios, and depending on the agroclimatic zones. Simulations were performed with the R570 cultivar. The current irrigation regime in each agroclimatic zone is indicated by I (irrigated areas) and NI (non-irrigated areas). The altitude range of agroclimatic zones is indicated by LA (low altitude) and HA (high altitude). A color gradient was added to improve visibility.